

Attempts to Synthesise Cantharidin.*

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According to the existing literature (Gadamer, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1914, 252, 624; 1916, 254, 423; 1920, 258, 171; Coffey, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1923, 42, 387, 1026) the most probable constitution of cantharidin is (I).

Although Bruchhausen and Bersch (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1928, 266, 697) obtained dehydroprotocanthalidin by condensing maleic anhydride with furan (*cf.* Diels, *Annalen*, 1927, 460, 98) which on reduction gave protocanthalidin, their attempt to synthesise dehydrocanthalidin from furan and dimethylmaleic anhydride was not successful. Their interesting observation that cantharidin on being passed over palladised asbestos at 280° is decomposed into furan and dimethylmaleic anhydride confirmed definitely the constitution of cantharidin as (I).

Iyer and Guha (*J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1931, 14A, 31) treated 1:2-dibromo-1:2-dimethylcyclohexane with an alcoholic solution of potassium cyanide to get the 1:2-dinitrile, the corresponding acid of which on anhydride formation was to give deoxycanthalidin. Their attempts, however, were unsuccessful, only unworkable resinous mass being formed in every case.

The next unsuccessful attempt to synthesise deoxycanthalidin was made by Steele (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 283) who prepared *aa'*-dibromo-*aa'*-dimethylsuberic acid and attempted the elimination of the two bromine atoms with copper-bronze or molecular silver in order to obtain the anhydride of *cis*-1:2-dimethylcyclohexane-1:2-dicarboxylic acid.

An attempt has now been made to synthesise cantharidin starting from methyl 3:6-diketocyclohexane-1:2-dicarboxylate (II) according to the following scheme:

* A preliminary report on this work has been published in the abstracts of papers, Chemistry section, *Indian Science Congress*, 1933, p. 18 and was communicated before the 15th October, 1932.

C-Dialkyl derivatives analogous to (III) have been prepared by Baeyer from succinosuccinic ester (*Ber.*, 1892, **25**, 2122; 1893, **26**, 232; Zelinsky and Naumow, *ibid.*, 1898, **31**, 3206).

From the disodium derivative of (II) and methyl iodide, Helferich (*Ber.*, 1921, **54**, 155) prepared methyl 2-methyl-3:6-diketocyclohexane-1:2-dicarboxylate. In a second paper, Helferich and Bondenbender (*Ber.*, 1923, **56**, 1112) report that although the ester (II) contains two monoalkylated acetoacetic ester residues it does not give a di-*C*-methyl derivative and they do not give any experimental data. Since the method of attack outlined above for the synthesis of cantharidin seemed rather an attractive one, methylation has now been tried under varying conditions with a view to obtaining the desired *cis-C*-dimethyl compound.

The disodium derivative, however, reacts with methyl iodide when left in a closed bottle at the room temperature for 3 weeks to give a 60-70% yield of a neutral oil. Both analytical values and molecular weight agree with the formula $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_6$, but the substance does not give any semicarbazone or phenylhydrazone. Methoxyl determination by the Zeisel method, however, gives a value of 45.15%. The *C*-dimethyl derivative (III) should give a methoxyl value 24.22% while the *O*-dimethyl compound (V) should give 48.44%. It would seem, therefore, that the product is the dimethyl ester contaminated possibly with some of the mono-*C*-methyl derivative (VI).

The pure dimethyl ether has now been prepared by treating an alcoholic solution of the diketo diester (II) with dimethyl sulphate and aqueous alcoholic potassium hydroxide. When hydrolysed by means of an excess of aqueous alcoholic potash, the ring breaks up at the double bonds giving succinic acid as one of the products of decomposition; hydrolysis with boiling 10% sulphuric acid gives 1:4-diketocyclohexane. The ester slowly absorbs bromine in chloroform solution and decolorises an aqueous acetone solution of potassium permanganate. These facts show without doubt that the product is the methyl ester of 3:6-dimethoxy-4:5-dihydrophthalic acid (V).

The explanation for the anomaly, *viz.*, the formation of the dimethyl ether in this manner, and in such good yield and that of the mono-*C*-methyl derivative (Helferich, *loc. cit.*) is perhaps to be found in the difference of temperatures at which the reactions were carried out. The effect of temperature and solvent on the keto-enol equilibrium is well known (*cf.* Meyer, *Annalen*, 1911, 380, 212; *Ber.*, 1911, 44, 2718, 2799). An experiment in which the reaction mixture was kept in an ice-chamber for one month yielded only the mono-*C*-methyl compound.

An attempt to introduce a second methyl group through the potassium derivative of Helferich's mono-*C*-methyl compound has resulted in the formation of a *neutral* oil, which from methoxyl determination, appears to be a mixture of *C*-dimethyl (III) and *C*-methyl-*O*-methyl (VI) derivatives almost in equal quantities.

The diketo diester (II) with sodamide and methyl iodide (*cf.* Haller and Louvrier, *Compt. rend.*, 1914, 158, 754, 1616; Ruzicka, *Ber.*, 1917, 50, 1373; Baker, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1551) in an atmosphere of nitrogen gave only the mono-*C*-methyl derivative. Treatment of the silver salt with methyl iodide has not been possible as the alcoholic solutions of the disodium salt of (II) and of silver nitrate gave immediately on mixing a black precipitate and mirror of metallic silver. The use of copper salt of methyl 2-methylcyclohexane-3:6-dione-1:2-dicarboxylate and methyl iodide (*cf.* Nef, *Annalen*, 1893, 276, 200) has not been successful.

Renewed attempts to synthesise deoxycantharidin according to the scheme of Iyer and Guha (*loc. cit.*) were made according to the method of Rosenmund and Struck (*Ber.*, 1919, 52, 1749) using cuprous cyanide as a catalyst with little success.

The synthesis of cantharidin is being tried starting from oxalyl diglycollic ester and succinyl dimethyldimalonic ester* results of which will form the subject of a subsequent communication.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Methyl 3:6-diketocyclohexane-1:2-dicarboxylate (II) was prepared according to Helferich's method (*loc. cit.*) via 2:3-dicyanohydroquinone and 3:6-dihydroxyphthalic acid with the following modifications.

2:3-Dicyanohydroquinone.—A three-necked flask (F) of 3-litre capacity (Fig. 1) is fitted with a mechanical stirrer (M), two separating funnels (S_1 and S_2), an exit tube (E) and a tube (T) to draw out the liquid. The tube (T) can be lowered into the flask when required. In the bell-jar (J) is placed a 2½-litre beaker containing crushed ice and the stopper of the bell-jar carries a tube connected with a water-jet pump. The whole apparatus is arranged in a fume cupboard fitted with a good exhaust fan.

FIG. 1.

* This method is being worked out in collaboration with Mr. B. H. Iyer.

Powdered benzoquinone (33 g.) suspended in hot water (400 c.c., 80-90°) was taken in the flask and 5*N*-sulphuric acid (110 c.c.) added. The mechanical stirrer was then started vigorously, and from the separating funnel (S_1) was added a concentrated aqueous solution of 41 g. of pure sodium cyanide during 3 to 4 minutes. When the colour became deep green 5*N*-sulphuric acid (115 c.c.) was introduced from the funnel (S_2). The stirring was then stopped, the tube (T) lowered to the bottom of the flask, and the water-pump started, the solution rose in the tube and was discharged into the beaker containing about 2 lbs. of powdered ice. The solution deposited a brown solid (19 g.) which was crystallised from hot water (charcoal) as lustrous straw-yellow plates, charring at 230°. When left in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid, it loses its water of crystallisation and becomes almost white.

3:6-Dihydroxyphthalic acid.—The hydrolysis of the dinitrile was carried out essentially according to Helferich's method, except that smaller quantities of the nitrile (15 g.) and excess of potash (216 g.) were used in each experiment. It was found preferable to extract the acidified solution with ethyl acetate instead of ether.

Methylation of Methyl cycloHexane-3:6-dione-1:2-dicarboxylate (II).

(a) *With sodium methoxide in methyl alcohol and methyl iodide*.—The following is typical of many experiments carried out by this method. Methyl cyclohexane-3:6-dione-1:2-dicarboxylate (6.8 g.) was taken in a round-bottomed flask (250 c.c.) fitted with a separating funnel, a condenser and inlet tube for passing nitrogen. The flask was first evacuated (3 mm.) by the Cenco pump and dry nitrogen passed slowly during the course of the reaction. To the clear solution obtained after the addition of absolute methyl alcohol (25 c.c.) was slowly added a solution of sodium (1.3 g.) in absolute methyl alcohol (35 c.c.). Methyl iodide (12 c.c.) was then introduced through the separating funnel to the clear dull yellow solution and the mixture heated under reflux on a water-bath for periods varying from 4 to 16 hours, fresh quantities of methyl iodide being added to make up for loss due to volatilisation. The residue after removal of alcohol and methyl iodide was acidified with 2*N*-sulphuric acid (25 c.c.), extracted with ether, and the extract washed with 2*N*-potassium hydroxide solution until the alkali solution was no longer coloured. The deep-red alkaline extracts after acidification with

2*N*-sulphuric acid was extracted with ether which gave a red oily residue. The solid separating out of this oil in a vacuum desiccator on long standing crystallised from methyl alcohol in fine prisms, m. p. 91-93°, and was identified with 2-*C*-methyl derivative of Helferich.

(b) *With sodium methoxide and methyl iodide at room temperature.*—A mixture of the diketo diester (11.4 g.), sodium methoxide prepared from sodium (2.3 g.), methyl iodide (18 c.c.) and absolute methyl alcohol (70 c.c.) was left in a stoppered bottle at the room temperature for 3 weeks. From the neutral reaction product alcohol and methyl iodide were removed under reduced pressure, water added to the residue and the mixture extracted with ether. The faintly yellow viscous oil obtained from the extract distilled without decomposition at 140-44°/1 mm., yield 7 g. It did not give any coloration with ferric chloride. (Found: C, 56.14; H, 6.11; OMe, 45.15. $C_{12}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 56.25; H, 5.25; OMe, 48.44 per cent).

(c) *With sodium hydroxide and dimethyl sulphate: Formation of the 3:6-dimethyl ether.*—To a solution of the diketo diester (10 g.) in methyl alcohol (20 c.c.) was added freshly distilled dimethyl sulphate (11.6 g.). To this mixture was poured slowly a solution of potassium hydroxide (2.6 g.) in water (5 c.c.) and alcohol (10 c.c.) with cooling. After removal of alcohol, the residue was treated with water and extracted with ether. The residue after removing the ether gave an oil distilling at 140-43°/1 mm., yield about 38%. The oil slowly absorbs bromine in chloroform solution and decolorises an aqueous acetone solution of potassium permanganate and potassium carbonate. (Found: C, 56.35; H, 6.33; OMe, 48.19. $C_{12}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 56.25; H, 6.25; OMe, 48.44 per cent).

(a) *Hydrolysis of Methyl 3:6-dimethoxy-4:5-dihydrophthalate (V).*—(i) *With sodium hydroxide.*—A mixture of the dimethoxy compound (4 g.) and an aqueous alcoholic solution of sodium hydroxide (6 g.) was kept for a day at the room temperature and then refluxed on the water-bath for 3 hours. The residue left after the removal of alcohol was acidified with 5*N*-sulphuric acid, the clear aqueous solution saturated with ammonium sulphate and then extracted with ether. The ethereal solution gave reddish oil from which a small quantity of a solid separated on standing in vacuum for 2 months. This melted at 179-80° and was identified as succinic acid by mixed m.p. with a genuine specimen (m.p. 180°).

(ii) *With sulphuric acid.*—The neutral ester (2 g.) mixed with concentrated sulphuric acid (8 c.c.) in 30 c.c. of water, was heated under reflux for 2 hours when the ester slowly went into solution with evolution of carbon dioxide. The solution was neutralised with sodium bicarbonate, saturated with ammonium sulphate and extracted four times with chloroform. The residue from chloroform crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 78°. The substance was identical with *cyclohexane-1:4-dione* obtained by hydrolysing (with 20% sulphuric acid) methyl *cyclohexane-2:5--dione-1:4-dicarboxylate*.

Methylation of Helferich's mono-C-methyl compound.—The potassium salt of the mono-*C*-methyl compound was prepared at 0° by means of potassium methoxide in dry methyl alcohol, methyl iodide added, and the mixture kept in a closed bottle for a day. By working up the product in the usual manner, a viscous neutral oil was isolated which did not give any coloration with ferric chloride. Owing to the small quantity obtained so far, purification of this substance has not been accomplished yet, but as a preliminary to determining its nature, a methoxyl determination was made. The observed methoxyl value of 30.61% is nearly the mean of the values for the *C*-dimethyl compound (III) (OMe, 24.22%) and the *C*-methyl-*O*-methyl derivative (VI) (OMe, 36.33%).

Interaction of potassium cyanide with 1:2-dibromo-1:2-dimethyl-cyclohexane.—A mixture of the dibromo compound (2.5 g.), pure potassium cyanide (2 g.), water (6 c.c.) containing cuprous cyanide (0.6 g.) (prepared according to the method of Sudborough and James, "Practical Organic Chemistry", p. 202) and ethyl alcohol (3 c.c.) was heated in a Carius tube at 200° for 8 hours. The contents of the tube after removal of alcohol were acidified with hydrochloric acid, the ether extract of which left on evaporation a small quantity of a neutral gum which did not crystallise. The aqueous solution was distilled in steam and the distillate extracted with ether. The ether extract did not yield any definite product and the aqueous solution deposited a tarry residue on standing. The experiment was repeated several times using soda water bottles and heating for longer periods with no better results.

